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ИНДИВІДУАЛІЗАЦІЯ ПРОЦЕСІВ ПІДГОТОВКИ ТА РОЗВИТКУ ПРАЦІВНИКІВ

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Ключові слова: успішність фахівця, професійна кар'єра, безробіття, якісна освіта, попит та пропозиція, індивідуалізація процесів підготовки.

ИНДИВИДУАЛИЗАЦИЯ ПРОЦЕССОВ ПОДГОТОВКИ И РАЗВИТИЯ РАБОТНИКОВ

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Предметом исследования является процесс подготовки и развития работников.

Цель исследования заключается в определении особенностей функционирования высших учебных заведений и обосновании целесообразности индивидуализации процессов подготовки и развития работников в соответствии с современными требованиями рынка труда.

Методологическую базу исследования составили научные труды отечественных и зарубежных ученых и ведущих специалистов, статистические и аналитические материалы органов государственной власти. В процессе исследования были использованы математический, аналитический и абстрактно-логический методы.

Результаты исследования. Установлено, что для полноценного использования трудового потенциала руководству и менеджерам субъектов хозяйствования всех форм собственности необходимо обеспечить получение не только дипломов о высшем образовании, ученой степени и т.д., но и качественных знаний по стратегическому управлению предприятием и персоналом в частности, организации и планированию бизнеса, управлению рисками, логистическому, инновационному и инвестиционному менеджменту и тому подобное. Доказано, что в современных условиях ведения бизнеса органы государственной власти и местного самоуправления совместно с представителями субъектов хозяйствования всех форм собственности заинтересованы в разработке согласованного механизма подготовки специалистов по актуальным учебным программам, что позволит не только снизить уровень безработицы среди экономически активного населения, но и создать действенную модель развития и улучшить общий уровень качества жизни. Выявлено существенную нехватку квалифицированных специалистов на отечественных субъектах хозяйствования всех форм собственности, что также подтверждается проведенным расчетом коэффициента эластичности и выявленным опережающим темпом роста объемов валового внутреннего продукта по сравнению с темпами роста численности экономически активного населения в возрасте 15-70 лет. Обоснована целесообразность введения индивидуальных траекторий практической подготовки будущих специалистов в качестве дополнительного обоснования и стимулирования получения высшего образования среди потенциальных абитуриентов.

Область применения результатов. Результаты исследования могут быть использованы всеми заинтересованными сторонами, в том числе органами государственной власти и местного самоуправления, высшими учебными заведениями и ведущими предприятиями региона.

Выводы. Внедрение разработанных мероприятий позволит уменьшить размер расходов, которые предприятие может понести при обучении молодых специалистов непосредственно на рабочем месте (в виде дополнительной заработной платы для учителей-наставников), продолжительность адаптационного периода, что будет способствовать достижению высокого уровня производительности труда в кратчайшие сроки.

Ключевые слова: успешность специалиста, профессиональная карьера, безработица, качественное образование, спрос и предложение, индивидуализация процессов подготовки.

INDIVIDUALIZATION OF PROCESSES FOR PREPARATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF WORKERS

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The subject of the study is the process of training and development of workers.

The purpose of the study is to determine the peculiarities of the functioning of institutions of higher education and to substantiate the expediency of individualizing the processes of training and development of employees in accordance with modern labor market requirements.

The methodological basis of the research consisted of scientific works of domestic and foreign scientists and leading specialists, statistical and analytical materials of state authorities. In the process of research, mathematical, analytical and abstract-logical methods were used.

Research results. It has been established that for full use of labor potential managers and managers of business entities of all forms of ownership should receive not only diplomas for higher education, academic degree, etc., but also qualitative knowledge on strategic management of the enterprise and personnel, in particular, organization and business planning, risk management, logistics, innovation and investment management, etc. It has been proved that in today's business environment, public authorities and local self-government bodies, together with representatives of business entities of all forms of ownership, are interested in developing a co-ordinated mechanism for training specialists for relevant curricula that will not only reduce the unemployment rate among the economically active population, but and create an effective model of development and improve the overall quality of life. The essential shortage of qualified specialists in domestic subjects of management of all forms of ownership was revealed, which is also confirmed by calculations of the coefficient of elasticity and revealed by a faster growth rate of gross domestic product in comparison with the growth rates of the economically active population aged 15-70. The feasibility of introducing individual trajectories of practical training of future specialists as additional justification and stimulation of higher education among potential applicants is substantiated.

The field of application of results. The results of the study can be used by all stakeholders, including public authorities and local self-government, higher education institutions and leading enterprises in the region.

Conclusions. Implementation of the measures developed will reduce the costs that the entity may incur when training young professionals directly at the workplace (in the form of additional salary for mentoring teachers), the duration of the adaptation period and will contribute to the achievement of a high level of productivity at the earliest possible time.

Keywords: successful specialist, professional career, unemployment, qualitative education, supply and demand, individualization of training processes.

Relevance of research topic. The search and training of talented employees whose knowledge and experience will enable business to achieve strategic goals is a key task for the top management of any business entity. At the same time, current business realities indicate that quite often at enterprises, institutions and organizations in the presence of talented and capable young people, as a result of incompetence of personnel staff, ineffective use of personal and professional capacity of staff is not taken into account, the real psychophysiological abilities of employees to perform the established functional responsibilities. As a result, employees' motivation for self-improvement decreases, which leads not only to the reduction of labor productivity, but also to the growth of its tension, the level of shortage and waste in production. As a basis, permanent, but ineffective, delays after the working day due to late implementation of proven plan tasks, which leads to an increase in the probability of possible injury due to violation of the rhythms of life and safety. That is why there is a need for a broad study of the factors that determine the qualitative characteristics of the qualification level of the labor potential of the enterprise, and the individualization of the processes of training and development of employees.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The study of the peculiarities of the labor activity of the population and the individualization of the processes of training and development of employees was carried out in their analytical works as specialists of state authorities (State Statistics Service of Ukraine, Ministry of Economic Development and Trade of Ukraine) [2, 6, 7, 10], and representatives of the scientific community : A.A. Derkach, V.G. Zazikin, A.K. Markov [1], N. Oliinyk [5], G. Pivnyak, A. Azyukovsky, M. Tregub, A. Bardas [8], B.T. Lozovetskaya [9], E. Stashkova [11], S.O. Tsimbalyuk [12], I.V. Sharapa [13], N.A. Tyuhtenko [14]. Despite the considerable tensions, there remain problems that require additional scientific analysis, especially as regards the qualitative characteristics of the qualification level of the labor potential of the enterprise and the individualization of the processes of training and development of employees.

The subject of the study is the process of training and development of workers.

The purpose of the study is to determine the peculiarities of the functioning of institutions of higher education and to substantiate the expediency of individualizing the processes of training and development of employees in accordance with modern labor market requirements.

The objectives of the study are: the definition of components of the specialist's success; identification of the main factors of the right choice of profession; analysis of the main indicators of the activity of higher educational institutions of Ukraine; Identification of the relationship between the indicators of the overall need of the national economy in the specialists with the most important socio-economic indicators of the country's development; substantiation of expediency of introduction of individual trajectories of practical training of future specialists.

The methodological basis of the research consisted of scientific works of domestic and foreign scientists and leading specialists, statistical and analytical materials of state authorities. In the process of research, mathematical, analytical and abstract-logical methods were used.

Formulation of the problem. Little-researched and insufficiently comprehensive studies in literary publications remain issues related to the formation of future professionals' ideas about the conditions and prospects of their own career in a market environment, relevant career perspectives of the modern personality. The foregoing determines the need for more thorough study of the theoretical and practical aspects of this problem and the introduction of further individualization of the processes of training and development of employees.

Research results. In modern conditions of operation, every head of an enterprise, which seeks to ensure effective and cost-effective operation, not only in the short-term, but also in the long-term perspective, must constantly implement measures associated of maximizing profitability, with updating the knowledge gained and increasing the professional competence of subordinates. Formation of an optimal strategy of support and development of individual abilities of an individual is the most important component of the further effective functioning of economic entities of all forms of ownership and of the national economy in general. The lack of a well-grounded strategy at the interval of primary education and further training can lead to training of specialists for non relevant and non competitive specialties. This will lead to an increase in unemployment, especially among young people, and a loss of incentives to acquire knowledge in educational institutions. Not always, alumni, even with a high level of grades, correspond to the professional competencies that are advanced to this qualification in the labor market [3].

A. Derkach [1] noted that the success of a specialist is determined by a set of special, general knowledge and abilities, as well as the compliance of the individual with the requirements for psychological, psychophysiological, socio-psychological qualities of future specialists.

One of the conditions for the formation of competitive labor resources in the relevant segment of the market is the awareness of future specialists of the need for constant support and development of individual professional abilities. Specialized labor force in the conditions of robotizing production processes is of great importance, but, unfortunately, specialized education in Ukraine almost does not pay attention. Often, you can observe employees who, having held positions of managers in the relevant areas of economic activity, do not have qualitative education and do not undergo courses for increasing professional competencies in a certain type of economic activity.

When employing workers whose education corresponds to their further direction of activity, the private sector has insignificant advantages compared to workers without specialized education, which is confirmed by the results of the activities of «professional adapters». At the same time, the problem lies in the fact that the owners of the company do not see this problem. However, neglecting the above can lead to a decrease in labor productivity and overall efficiency of economic activity. Undervalued knowledge obtained in the process of studying a particular specialty.

One can agree with the author [9] that the prerequisite for a successful professional career is the right choice of profession. The solution to this problem is based on an analysis of several factors, namely:

- You need to know well the world of professions and the requirements imposed on a person who performs one or another work;
- You need to correctly identify your interests and inclinations, evaluate your ability, state of health, ability and compliance with the requirements of the chosen profession;
- It is necessary to study the state of the labor market, its needs and regional features;
- You need to start from real opportunities for education, retraining and advanced training.

Carrying out the above analysis will allow to choose the necessary profession, to outline your professional route and to choose an individual way to achieve the set goal.

Exploring the conditions for the formation of professional self-consciousness, E. Stažhkova [11] concluded that this phenomenon has a dual nature, elemental and dynamic, and includes the stages of origin, development and formation. Professional formation of a person is determined by the level of formation of professional consciousness. At the same time, the period of active formation of professional self-awareness begins after the choice of the profession or the beginning of the work of a graduate school. Such a process, in the majority of cases, means ending doubts about the correctness of the decision taken in the professional choice, while a person can go up the «professional ladder» by raising and expanding his skills, or changing his profession, place of work and qualification as a result of an unjustified choice of professional activity.

Earlier studies [3, 4] show that rising unemployment among the population aged 15 to 29 years in most cases is associated with the psychological peculiarities of the male group of this age when choosing the direction of further intellectual and professional development with the ease of obtaining knowledge and «melodious sounding» the names of specialty and specialization of qualification level of preparation without taking into account the forecast trends in the relevant market of labor resources in the future. For full use of labor potential management and managers of business entities, especially agricultural enterprises, it is necessary to ensure that they receive not only diplomas for higher education, academic degree, etc., but also qualitative knowledge on strategic management of the enterprise and personnel, in particular, organization and business planning, risk management, logistics, innovation and investment management, etc. This is necessary for the development and formation of a sound strategy for increasing the competitiveness of the enterprise in general, and for using and developing the personnel as the most important component in particular.

Consequently, in modern conditions of doing business the main thing is not getting a diploma about the graduation of higher education institution, but obtaining additional qualitative knowledge and skills in the chosen and actual direction of activity. It is also possible to agree with the authors [8] that without changes in the work of general educational institutions, the higher school of Ukraine runs the risk of being trapped when the domination of the humanities will significantly exceed the demand for the labor market and thus contribute to the reduction of the prestige of higher education in general and disappointment of the general population. In those social opportunities of development, which gives people a better education. It is necessary to solve this with the participation of universities at the same time as the introduction of students' professional orientation in schools, the formation of the ability to independent thinking, responsible decision-making and planning of their own lives.

The training of future specialists in Ukraine for the 2015/2016 academic year was carried out by 659 higher educational establishments, including I-II accreditation levels - 371 units, III-IV accreditation levels - 288 units. The dynamics of the main indicators of activity of higher educational institutions of Ukraine is reflected in Table 1.

The results of the analysis carried out in Table 1 show that the number of students obtaining a higher education in the chosen specialty is steadily decreasing. In the 2015/2016 academic year, compared to the 2010/2011 academic year, the reduction was from 33.5% in higher education institutions of the III-IV accreditation levels to 34.5% in higher education institutions of the I and II accreditation levels. At the same time, the number of institutions trained by future specialists decreased only from 12.7% among institutions of higher education of III - IV accreditation levels to 23.2% among institutions of higher education of I - II levels of accreditation. The above is connected, first of all, with changing the system of preparing students from mass to individual coverage by reducing the number of students in groups and focusing on the performance of individual work within the material outlined in lecture and seminar sessions.

Also, given the low wages in scientific and pedagogical workers, there is a negative tendency to decrease their qualitative indicators in higher education institutions. Thus, despite the relatively simplified conditions for obtaining the academic title of associate professor and professor from 2011 to 2015, the total number of said employees in higher education institutions of the III-IV accreditation levels in the 2015/2016 academic year decreased from 4.9% for associate professors to 5.6% among professors compared to the 2010/2011 school year.

When we are analyzing the qualitative component of scientific and pedagogical workers of institutions of higher education, it is necessary to take into account also the fact that the mandatory condition for admission to the postgraduate / doctorate program at the expense of state and local budgets is a guarantee from the institution

regarding the further employment of a postgraduate / doctoral student with successful protection and obtaining the appropriate degree. As a result, the largest proportion of those who defended the dissertation work in the relevant higher education institutions. Also, the largest proportion among doctors of philosophy (candidates of science) is occupied by researchers, whose average age is 30-39 years (29.3% of the total). The proportion of researchers over the age of 60 years is 22.8%. Among doctors of sciences, these indicators are 4.2% and 56.7% respectively.

Table 1. Dynamics of Changes in Key Performance Indicators of Ukrainian Higher Educational Institutions*

Indicator	Educational years						Rate of growth (decrease),%	
	2010/11	2011/12	2012/13	2013/14	2014/15	2015/16	2015/16 2010/11	2015/16 2014/15
I - II levels of accreditation								
Number of institutions, units	483	479	469	458	387	371	76,8	95,9
Number of students, thousand persons	351,4	347,2	335,9	319,6	251,3	230,1	65,5	91,6
Accepted, thousands of people	125,1	102,2	96,7	90,9	69,5	63,2	50,5	90,9
Thousands of people were released	107,4	94,0	89,8	88,7	79,1	73,4	68,3	92,8
The number of students per 10 thousand population	81	80	78	74	59	54	66,7	91,5
Teaching staff, persons:								
1. Teachers:								
- Candidates of Sciences	937	964	951	986	949	1016	108,4	107,1
- Doctor of Sciences	58	56	55	43	49	60	103,4	122,4
- Associate Professors	341	328	325	288	271	245	71,8	90,4
- Professors	56	57	53	44	42	54	96,4	128,6
2. Scientific and pedagogical workers:								
- Candidates of Sciences	114	121	83	89	126	170	149,1	134,9
- Doctor of Sciences	23	23	18	14	17	34	147,8	200,0
- Associate Professors	52	58	25	37	51	62	119,2	121,6
- Professors	22	20	19	17	19	33	150,0	173,7
III - IV levels of accreditation								
Number of institutions, units	330	326	316	309	277	288	87,3	104,0
Amount of students, millions of people	2,07	1,9	1,77	1,67	1,44	1,38	66,5	95,6
Accepted, thousands of people	381,4	307,3	331,2	337,4	291,6	259,9	68,2	89,1
Thousands of people were released	528,9	515,0	505,4	471,7	405,4	374,0	70,7	92,3
The number of students per 10 thousand population	476	439	410	389	335	322	67,6	96,1
Teaching staff, persons:								
1. Teachers:								
- Candidates of Sciences	529	604	658	772	796	1151	217,6	144,6
- Doctor of Sciences	22	28	18	29	33	67	304,5	203,0
- Associate Professors	205	229	226	264	256	364	177,6	142,2
- Professors	15	26	16	24	22	45	300,0	204,5
2. Scientific and pedagogical workers:								
- Candidates of Sciences	66689	67057	67675	69582	62158	61266	91,9	98,6
- Doctor of Sciences	13367	13436	13826	14269	12682	13072	97,8	103,1
- Associate Professors	44608	45060	46127	47416	42600	42414	95,1	99,6
- Professors	12158	12211	12484	12609	11249	11476	94,4	102,0

* Compiled and calculated on the basis of [6]

The above analysis shows that the greatest proportion among scientific researchers and scientific and pedagogical workers is occupied by persons whose age is not more than 40 years, which indicates a relatively small or even missing experience of practical work in the field of research conducted, or exceeds 60 years, that in the conditions of rapid pace of change of scientific and technological progress, testifies to «moral obsolete» practical training of the given staff, obtained during the Soviet Union.

In today's business environment, public authorities and local self-government bodies, together with representatives of business entities of all forms of ownership, are interested in developing a coherent mechanism for training specialists for current curricula, which will not only reduce the unemployment rate among economically active population, but also create effective development model and improve the overall quality of life. It is necessary to determine the correlation of the indicators of the general need of the national economy in the specialists with the

most important socio-economic indicators of the country's development: gross domestic product, volume of industrial production, average number of economically active population, etc.

The conducted research of the influence of economic activity of the population aged 15-70 [2] on the total gross domestic product [7] in 2010-2015 allowed to construct the following single-factor linear regression (correlation coefficient $r_{yx1} = 0.937$):

$$Y = -101720.14 + 58.75 * X_1, \quad (1)$$

where Y - gross domestic product at constant prices in 2010, UAH million;

X_1 - is the average number of economically active population aged 15-70, thsd.

The indicator $A_0 = -101720.14$ indicates a significant shortage of qualified specialists in domestic entities of all forms of ownership, which is also confirmed by calculations of the elasticity coefficient and the outstripping rate of growth of gross domestic product in comparison with the growth rates of the number of economically active population aged 15-70 years old.

It is also noteworthy that the largest number of institutions of higher education involved in the training of students in the field of knowledge 07 «Management and administration». Thus, according to the Decrees of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated April 29, 2015 № 266 and from February 1, 2017, № 53, training is carried out in the following specialties:

- 071 «Accounting and Taxation» - 453 institutions of higher education;
- 072 «Finance, Banking and Insurance» - 431 units;
- 073 «Management» - 379 units;
- 075 Marketing - 178 units;
- 076 «Entrepreneurship, trade and stock-taking activity» - 295 units.

At the same time, one of the largest burdens of registered unemployed in 2015 and 2016 was observed among legislators, senior civil servants, managers, managers (managers) - respectively 352 and 239 per 10 vacancies [10]. This confirms the imbalance of demand and supply both in terms of numbers and structure of specialties in the labor market.

On the example of the Faculty of Economics and Management of the Kherson State University, it was found that according to the results of the entry companies in 2016 and 2017, only about 13% of applicants enrolled in the first year in the corresponding specialties acquired the right to study at the expense of state-commissioned funds.

The total cost of education, despite its relatively low level in comparison with the 2013/2014 school year, in conditions of depreciation of incomes is unacceptable for parents and university entrants. As a result, there is an annual decrease in the number of entrants, including those specializing in economics and management of economic entities of all forms of ownership.

The solution to this situation is not only to improve the recruiting and popularization system of Kherson State University and the Faculty in particular, but also to introduce individual trajectories of practical training of future specialists as additional justification and stimulation of higher education among potential entrants. This is possible through the involvement of the heads of leading enterprises, institutions and organizations not only in the direction of examination commissions in the certification of applicants, but also in the joint formation of a list of selective academic disciplines with higher education institutions and relevant students. In accordance with clause 15 of paragraph 1 of Article 62 of the Law of Ukraine «On Higher Education», persons studying in higher education institutions have the right to choose educational disciplines within the limits provided for by the relevant educational program and curriculum in a volume which is not less than 25 percent of the total number of ECTS credits provided for this level of higher education. Particularly relevant are the measures will be for students who will be willing to work in the future for these enterprises. Consequently, the system for the implementation of independent and individual tasks for this group of students should also cover the future employment field. The passage of all types of practice for this group of students should take place directly at the workplaces of certain business entities, with the fulfillment of standard tasks and payment of labor on the part of the employer in accordance with the current legislation.

On the example of the Kherson region, we can state that in the presence of the appropriate legislative mechanism in this area Kherson State University can cooperate with the following leading enterprises of the region: «Amalteya» Ltd and its partners, «Avtoplanet» auto-holding (LLC «Avtoplaneta Plus» LLC «Center Kherson», LLC «Foltsvagen Center Kherson»). Experts from the Department of Economic Development and Trade of Kherson Oblast State Administration, Kherson Regional Interdepartmental Council of Trade Unions and the Kherson Regional Organization of the Trade Union of Textile and Light Industry Workers are ready to receive and share practical experience on a free-of-charge basis.

Thus, during the course of practice and participation in business trainings, which will be conducted by experienced specialists of Amalteya Ltd, the scientific-pedagogical staff and students of the faculty will be involved in the development of perspective business projects in the framework of the industrial park for the development of objects that have strategic importance for the economy and security of the region and the country in general. As a result of the practice, students should present the developed projects and prove their validity and economic feasibility. When implementing these measures, all participants receive appropriate material incentives from the management of «Amalteya» Ltd., and the best group of students will have the right to work at this enterprise. Also, students involved in the implementation of the specified project, for example, from the specialty 073 «Management», will in practice test and verify the actuality of the acquired knowledge of a set of disciplines of professional and practical training, such as: «Management and administration» (23.5 ECTS credits respectively to the curriculum), «State and Regional

Administration» (4.5), «Marketing» (3.5), «Logistics» (3), «Organizational Behavior» (3), «Business Planning» (3), «Communicative Management» (3).

With the auto-holding «Autoplanet», the following arrangements can be reached: during the acquisition of the second master's degree in higher education from the specialty 073 «Management. Business Administration» employees of the autoholding company should develop and offer new actual directions of further development of the relevant facilities, where they perform their functional duties. According to the results of open data protection projects within the activity of the examination commissions, the employees will receive appropriate assessment from the members of the examination commission (on a 100 scale scale) and from the top management of the autoholding company «Avtoplaneta» in the form of a certain percentage of the compensation of expenses for training at the expense of the enterprise. The percentage of compensation for costs will depend on the quality of the research carried out and will be carried out in the form of additional bonuses for employees.

Conclusion. Implementation of the above measures will reduce the costs that an entity may incur when training young professionals directly at the workplace (in the form of additional salary for mentoring teachers), the duration of the adaptation period and will contribute to the achievement of a high level of productivity at the earliest possible time.

In order to stimulate the participation of business in these activities it would be advisable to borrow the experience of leading countries of the world and allow to reduce the amount of financial result before tax from the economic activity of the enterprise for a double amount of expenditure spent on obtaining additional education workers in higher education institutions in the directions of the operation of this entity management.

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ДЕРЖАВНЕ РЕГУЛЮВАННЯ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ СФЕРИ ОБСЛУГОВУВАННЯ

Почтарьов С.О.

Предметом статті виступає державне регулювання сфери обслуговування, як надважливої ланки економіки країни в цілому.

Метою самого дослідження є формулювання науково обґрунтованого визначення поняття державного регулювання сфери обслуговування.

В ході роботи було здійснено аналіз останніх публікацій як вітчизняних, так і закордонних дослідників в галузі економіки.

У статті обґрунтовано роль державного регулювання діяльності сфери обслуговування, розкрито його сутність. Окреслено форми й методи, а також можливі шляхи оптимізації розвитку сфери обслуговування в Україні. Визначено роль і місце сфери обслуговування у розвитку економіки України. Результати дослідження можуть використовуватися в галузі економіки при подальшому вивченні функціонування сфери обслуговування.

Сфера обслуговування як продуктивно-перспективна галузь в національній економіці України відіграє ключову роль у формуванні постіндустріального економічно стабільного суспільства але її діяльність потребує регулювання з боку держави.

Ключові слова: державне регулювання, сфера обслуговування, зростання економіки, розвиток, діяльність.

ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЕ РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЕ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СФЕРЫ ОБСЛУЖИВАНИЯ

Почтарёв С.А.

Предметом статьи выступает государственное регулирование сферы обслуживания, как сверхважного звена экономики страны в целом.

Целью же исследования является формулирование научно обоснованного определения понятия государственного регулирования сферы обслуживания.

В ходе работы был осуществлен анализ последних публикаций как отечественных, так и зарубежных исследователей в области экономики.

В статье обоснована роль государственного регулирования деятельности сферы обслуживания, раскрыто его сущность. Определены формы и методы, а также возможные пути оптимизации развития сферы обслуживания в Украине. Определены роль и место сферы обслуживания в развитии экономики Украины. Результаты исследования могут использоваться в области экономики при дальнейшем изучении функционирования сферы обслуживания.

Сфера обслуживания как продуктивно-перспективная отрасль в национальной экономике Украины играет ключевую роль в формировании постиндустриального экономически стабильного общества но ее деятельность требует регулирования со стороны государства.

Ключевые слова: государственное регулирование, сфера обслуживания, рост экономики, развитие, деятельность.

STATE REGULATION OF THE SERVICE SECTOR ACTIVITY

Pochtarov S.O.

The subject of the article is the state regulation of the sphere of service, as an overriding part of the economy of the country as a whole.

The purpose of the study itself is to formulate a scientifically based definition of the concept of state regulation of the service sector.